

Supplementary Material - Spatial Omics Driven Crossmodal Pretraining Applied to Graph-based Deep Learning for Pathology Analysis

	Contrastive Crossmodal Spatial Pretraining	Downstream Outcome GCNs (n=3)
Epochs	150	30
Learning Rate	0.00001	0.001
Batch Size	8	8

Table S1: Hyperparameters for models trained during this study.

Figure S2: Additional example visualizations of KMeans clustering-derived subgroups in WSI, identified using various patch embedding mechanisms.

Figure S3: Additional example visualizations of KMeans clustering-derived subgroups in WSI, identified using various patch embedding mechanisms.

Figure S4: Boxplot visualizations of predicted lymph node metastasis risk versus localization status of tumor infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) by GCN models utilizing patch embeddings derived by the Ciga et al method, and the developed spatial crossmodal pretraining method.